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Growth and survival rate of bonylip barb (*Osteochilus vittatus*) in round water flowing container

**Ayi Yustiati, Muhammad Titan Sad'inawa Rojai*,
Ibnu Bangkit Bioshina Suryadi, Iskandar**

Fisheries Departement, Faculty of Fisheries and Marine Science, Universitas Padjadjaran,
Bandung – Sumedang KM. 21, Jatinangor 45363, Indonesia

*E-mail address: Muhammad16119@mail.unpad.ac.id

ABSTRACT

This research is done to reveal the effect of water flow on the round container to increase the growth and survival rate in bonylip barb. The method used in this research is an experimental method using a Completely Random Design (CRD) which is consist of three treatments and five repetitions. The treatments are round container without water flow (A), round container with $0,1 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ of water flow (B) and round container with $0,1 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ of water flow with an additional venturi aerator. The numbers of bonylip barb fingerlings used in this research are 900 with a length of 1-3 cm. The container used in this research is 15 water gallons with a volume of 19L. The density of the container is 60 fish per container. Fish maintained for 40 days. The feeding rate given is 5% of the biomass. The observed parameters are survival rate, daily growth rate and feed conversion ratio observed every 10 days. The result showed that the water flow combined with the venturi aerator give the best result with 77.3% of survival rate, 3.12% of daily growth rate and 1.42 feed conversion ratio.

Keywords: Bonylip barb, fingerlings, water flow, venturi, round container, *Osteochilus vittatus*

1. INTRODUCTION

Bonylip barb (*Osteochilus vittatus*) is an endemic Indonesian fish that lives in freshwaters, such as rivers and swamps. Bonylip barb is one of the aquaculture commodities that have economic value, because bonylip barb fish is very popular with the public, both for cultivation and as processed food products. This is evidenced based on data from the Directorate General of Aquaculture (DJBP) regarding the production target of bonylip barb cultivation in 2014-2019 of 242,800 tons with an annual increase of 15%.

The problem that many cultivators face is slow growth. Bonylip barb requires a lot of energy because bonylip barb is used to living in rivers where the activity is much greater than in ponds or in calm water. Growth can occur when fish have excess energy because bonylip barb tend to use more energy compared to growth.

Intensive bonylip barb cultivation is also constrained by the decline in water quality due to the accumulation of waste generated in aquaculture activities. Water quality is one of the environmental factors that affect the growth and survival of fish. How to improve water quality can use recirculating cultivation systems, conventional, bioflocs and the use of currents.

The use of flow in the system is expected to produce optimal growth and survival of fish. Fish farming in flowing or moving water systems can have a significant impact on fish growth, because there is higher dissolved oxygen. Regardless of the availability of dissolved oxygen, currents stimulate fish to keep moving.

One system of flow-generating equipment that can be used in aquaculture activities is the use of a venturi aerator. The application of this system is expected to have a better impact that can increase production yields for farmed fish.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Photo 1. *Osteochilus vittatus* (Valenciennes, 1842)

The tools used in this research are 15 gallons containing 15 liters of water, 10 buckets, 10 sets of PVC pipes, 10 pumps with 30 watts of power, 3 aerators, 5 venturi aerators, digital scales, millimeter blocks, stationery, scoop net and dacron. The materials used were fish feed with a protein content of 39-41% and bonylip barb fingerlings measuring 1-3 cm which was obtained from UPT Pembenhian Ikan Ciparay, Bandung Regency.

The research method was carried out experimentally using the Completely Randomized Design (CRD) method. This research consisted of three treatments with five replications, namely the use of a circular container and the provision of current for maintenance with treatment A: A circular container with aeration without current; Treatment B: Round container with a current of 0.1 m s^{-1} ; Treatment C: Round container with a current of 0.1 m s^{-1} combined with a venturi aerator.

Photos 2(a,b). Laboratory work

2. 1. Preparation Phase

This research uses used gallons with a diameter of 26 cm and a height of 48 cm with a capacity of 19 liters of water as a maintenance container. Gallon as a container is designed to be able to produce a constant rotating current (Figures 1, 2 and 3). Water is flowed at a flow of 0.1 m s^{-1} with a recirculation system using a pump consisting of an inlet and outlet.

The method of determining the current 0.1 m s^{-1} is by measuring the circumference of the gallon, then using pieces of styrofoam to flow into the gallon that has been given a current and counting the time for one circumference.

Then the results of the calculation of the circumference of the gallon are divided by the time the Styrofoam surrounds the gallon, if the calculation results have not reached 0.1 m s^{-1} stop of the inlet faucet is adjusted to a current of 0.1 m s^{-1} .

Treatment A uses conventional aeration without flow as a source of oxygen in the container:

Figure 1. Treatment container design A

Treatment B uses a pump flow system as the oxygen source and without the addition of a venturi aerator at the inlet:

Figure 2. Treatment container design B

Treatment C uses a pump flow system that has a modification at the inlet in the form of an additional venturi aerator so that the flow that comes out is in the form of small bubbles as a source of oxygen:

Figure 3. Treatment container design C

3. MAIN RESEARCH

Fish rearing was carried out for 40 days using gallons as a maintenance container with each gallon containing 60 bonylip barb fingerlings. Feeding was carried out three times a day, namely at 08:00, 12:00 and 16:00 WIB. The feed given was adjusted to a feeding rate (FR) of 5% of the bonylip barb biomass and adjusted every ten days. Observations of survival were carried out every day, when there were dead fish the number was counted and their weight was weighed. Growth data were collected every ten days. The addition of water is done according to the amount of water wasted.

3. 1. Observation Parameters

The following are some of the parameters that will be observed during the research activities:

3. 1. 1. Survival Rate

Survival was observed every day, when any dead fish were counted, weighed and recorded. Survival rate of fish was determined using the formula according to:

$$SR = \frac{Nt}{No} \times 100\%$$

Note :

SR : Survival Rate (%)

Nt : Number of live fish at the end of fish rearing (40th day) (individual)

No : Number of fish at the beginning of fish rearing (individual)

3. 1. 2. Daily Growth Rate

The calculation of the daily growth rate of fish weight and length based on formula is as follows:

Weight :

$$\alpha = \frac{\ln Wt - \ln Wo}{t} \times 100\%$$

Note :

α : Daily growth rate (%)

Wt : Average weight fish at the end of fish rearing (40th day) (g)

Wo : Average weight fish at the beginning of fish rearing (g)

t : Duration of observation (40 days)

Length :

$$\alpha = \frac{\ln Lt - \ln Lo}{t} \times 100\%$$

Note :

α : Daily growth rate (%)

Wt : Average length fish at the end of fish rearing (40th day) (g)

Wo : Average length fish at the beginning of fish rearing (g)

t : Duration of observation (40 days)

3. 1. 3. Feed Conversion Ratio

Feed conversion ratio was determined using the formula according to:

$$FCR = \frac{F}{(Wt + D) - Wo}$$

Note :

FCR : Feed conversion ratio

F : Amount of feed given during the research (g)

Wt : Biomass at the end of fish rearing (40th day) (g)
Wo : Biomass at the start of fish rearing (g)
D : Biomass of fish that died during the observation (g)

3. 2. Data Analysis

Analysis of the data used for this research is analysis of variance with F test at 95% confidence level which is used to determine whether there is a significant difference between survival, weight growth rate, length growth rate and feed conversion ratio. If the treatments were significantly different, Duncan's test was performed.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following are the results and discussion of some of the observed growth parameters:

4. 1. Survival Rate

Survival rate is the percentage of test fish that live at the end of the rearing of the number of test fish stocked at the time of rearing in a container. That the survival rate is the percentage value of the number of fish that live during the maintenance period. The average survival of bonylip barb fingerling during research activities can be seen in Figure 4 below:

Figure 4. Survival Rate

The highest survival value was in treatment C with a value of 77.3%, then treatment B with a value of 73.3% and finally treatment A with a value of 70.7%. Based on the follow-up test using Duncan's test, treatment C was significantly different from treatment A and treatment B, treatment A and treatment B were not significantly different. The survival value obtained in the three research treatments is quite good because the value obtained is >70% for fish fry from the cyprinidae family with a length of 1-3 cm, survival is 70%.

The use of flow discharge with a venturi aerator produces the highest survival value. The microbubble produced by the venturi aerator makes the oxygen distribution more even and not easily diffused into the air. In contrast to ordinary bubbles, which are larger in size, they tend to diffuse faster into the air and enter the water body unevenly. The application of this system in a maintenance container, directly plays an important role in the availability of dissolved oxygen and improves water quality, this is in accordance with the statement of that with the recirculation discharge, the water in the test container is transported out more quickly so that the quality of the water in the maintenance container will be maintained and this can increase survival.

4. 2. Daily Growth Rate (Weight)

External factors such as environmental factors and feed are very influential on fish growth. These two factors will balance the state of the fish's body while in the rearing medium. The availability of feed has a major effect on the growth and survival of fish. The following is a graph of the average daily growth rate of bonylip barb fingerlings weight during research activities, which can be seen in Figure 5 below:

Figure 5. Daily Growth Rate (Weight)

The value of daily growth rate of bonylip barb fingerling weight during research activities got the highest value in treatment C with a value of 3.12%, for treatment B of 2.87% and treatment A getting a value of 2.59%. Based on the follow-up test using Duncan's test, treatment C was significantly different from treatment A, treatment B was significantly different from treatment A and treatment B was also significantly different from treatment C. This is related to the use of the system between treatment A and treatment B and C where the use of a recirculating system in maintenance containers makes the distribution of feed evenly and feed more efficient, even more so when the use of venturi gets the highest value. Although Treatments B and C both used a recirculation system, they were significantly different, due to

treatment C applying a venturi aeration system which produced microbubbles that could make oxygen last longer in the waters which could affect fish appetite, metabolism and growth.

Research on the growth rate of carp in closed flow system ponds conducted by, obtained a daily growth yield of smaller weights than treatments A, B and C, with a value of $1.75 \pm 0.03\%$ per day for fish fed pelleted feed as much as 3% of their body weight per day. This is in accordance with the question of that the environment is an external factor that affects the growth of fish.

4. 3. Daily Growth Rate (Lenght)

Environmental factors are very influential on the growth of fish. One of the environmental factors that can affect growth is currents, with the flow of water, metabolic waste substances will be carried away so that it will improve water quality. The following is a graph of the average daily growth rate of bonylip barb fingerlings length during research activities:

Figure 6. Daily Growth Rate (Lenght)

The graph in Figure 6 shows the value of the daily growth rate of bonylip barb fingerlings length obtained from the ANOVA test results, where these results show that the value is not significantly different. Of the three treatments, the highest value was obtained in treatment C with a value of 1.06%, then treatment B at 1.05% and finally treatment A at 0.99%. However, the values of the three treatments showed that the use of currents had an effect on the growth of fish seed length. This is in accordance with statement that the provision of current to fish rearing media experienced faster growth in length than those that did not.

4. 4. Feed Conversion Ratio

Feed conversion is the ratio of the amount of feed given to the total weight of the fish produced. The smaller the feed conversion value means the efficiency level of feed utilization is better, on the contrary if the feed conversion is large, the efficiency level of feed utilization

is not good. The following is a graph of the average feed conversion ratio for bonylip barb fingerlings during research activities, which can be seen in Figure 7 below:

Figure 7. Feed Conversion Ratio

Treatment A got a feed conversion ratio value of 1.81, which means 1.81 grams of feed produced 1 gram of fish weight. Treatment B resulted in a value of 1.65 which means 1.65 grams of feed given produced 1 gram of fish weight and treatment C got a value of 1.42 which also means 1.42 grams of feed produced 1 gram of fish weight. The value of the feed conversion ratio is influenced by several factors such as density, the weight of each individual, age of the group of animals, water temperature and feeding method (quality, quantity and frequency of feeding).

Based on Duncan's test, treatment A was significantly different from treatment B, treatment B was also significantly different from treatment C.

The results of regarding the growth of bonylip barb kept in aquariums, the average feed efficiency for 3% feeding treatment was 0.39 or had an average feed conversion of 2.56. This value is lower than the results of the research on treatment C which had the best average feed conversion value of 1.42. This is because in aquaculture with moving or flowing water the growth and weight of fish will be higher and this is because the resulting current is able to improve water quality and suppress metabolic waste and the feed factor provided is utilized optimally by fish.

5. CONCLUSION

The results of this research can be revealed that the use of circular with 0.1 m s⁻¹ current combined with the best treatment venturi aerator, resulted in the highest life use value of 77.3%, daily weight growth rate of 3.12% and conversion value feed of 1.42.

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